

EFFECTS OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON THE WELLBEING OF REGISTERED NURSES

by

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Abstract

The global outbreak of COVID-19, beginning in 2020, brought unprecedented burdens to the healthcare industry, especially to healthcare workers working on the frontlines. The impact on healthcare workers of working during a major public health crisis has been largely unknown prior to the pandemic. Three years into the pandemic, the negative impacts have been coming to the surface. Lasting effects of the pandemic on the mental health and well-being, job satisfaction and burnout levels of frontline healthcare workers were examined through in-depth interviews with four registered nurses working in different regions of Southern California. The interview questions covered various topics, including overwork, burnout, nurse incivility, chronic scheduling problems, job dissatisfaction, and other emotional impacts of working through the pandemic. Though specific circumstances were different for each respondent depending upon hospital, department, and personal experiences, all respondents spoke of pervasive negative experiences related to these factors. This research produces valuable qualitative data to supplement the growing body of evidence on the post-COVID-19 pandemic healthcare workforce crisis that includes surveys and other quantitative research, congressional testimony, and articles and reports in mass, professional, and scholarly media. First-person accounts of the pandemic's impact are critical to presenting the human side of this crisis.

Introduction

The outbreak of the SARS-CoV-2 virus that led to the COVID-19 pandemic and the deaths of 6.8 million people has created unprecedented burdens for global public health and the healthcare industry. While the pandemic was declared over in May 2023 (Center for Disease Control and Prevention, 2023), the impacts on healthcare workers' mental health, job satisfaction, and burnout levels are on-going – and their long-term effect remains largely unknown. The deterioration of healthcare workers' well-being caused by the pandemic has been recognized as a public health problem that can harm patient-care quality and the professional and personal lives of nurses, physicians, and other healthcare workers (Sovold et al., 2021). With the help of my faculty mentor, Dr. Carter Rakovski of the California State University, Fullerton, Department of Sociology, I conducted a research study on the long-term impacts of working through the COVID-19 pandemic on the wellbeing of registered nurses in Southern California. Qualitative research methods such as interviews and observational studies were utilized to determine the extent of the impacts of the pandemic on the mental health, job satisfaction, and professional burnout of registered nurses. These findings were synthesized with results from previously published literature in this field of research to determine if the experiences and effects felt by interview participants were also reported in other studies. The overall objective of this research study is to not only look at the effects on registered nurses of working through the pandemic, but also to explore sustainable solutions to the long-term problems that arose during the last three years. Healthcare workers play a vital role in society; optimal solutions are necessary to support nurses so that all people can receive the quality healthcare they need.

Methods

In order to better understand the pandemic's impact on mental health, wellbeing, burnout and job satisfaction among frontline registered nurses, in-depth interviews were conducted with registered nurses working at major medical centers in densely populated regions of Southern California, areas that were hard hit by COVID-19. Qualitative interview methods ensure that the subjective perceptions of frontline nurses are reported in the results of this research and provide individualized data based on the actual experiences of frontline healthcare workers during the pandemic.

Approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) to conduct research with human subjects was obtained prior to formal question development for interviews with registered nurses. Interview questions and categories were determined through a literature review of nurses' challenges while working during the pandemic along with my observations while volunteering at a large Southern California regional medical center in 2021-2022. The interview questions focused on nurses' experiences and perceptions related to incivility and bullying, scheduling difficulties, staffing shortages, scope of practice, impact on mental health and wellbeing, job satisfaction, caring for people with COVID-19, handling the physical and emotional demands of patients with COVID-19, and dealing with an unprecedented surge in patient census at hospitals.

The four registered nurses interviewed were selected through indirect personal contacts to avoid institutional oversight and allow the subjects to speak more candidly about their experiences. Nurses working in large, busy hospitals in various departments during the pandemic were chosen because they would provide personal experiences and perceptions of impacts, and because the COVID-19 pandemic was fresh in the minds of the nurses. The four nurses included a Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) nurse, a Post-Anesthesia Care Unit (PACU) nurse who

recently moved from the Intensive Care Unit (ICU), a surgical ICU nurse, and a radio ER nurse that takes incoming calls from first responders bringing patients to their emergency department that is also in an administrative role. All of these nurses had been working in the healthcare industry for a minimum of five years, with some of them working in the industry for nearly 35 years. The nurses' were located in Southern California, their ages ranged from early 30s to mid 60s and they were majority white and hispanic. The interview subjects were known to the interviewer but were not close contacts and had never discussed their nursing experiences with the interviewer.

Thirty to 45 minute interviews were conducted over the phone during December 2022. Results were synthesized and organized by question topic to determine similarities and differences among participants' responses. Analysis of the interview data was theme-based, focusing on the common problem areas identified in the nurses' experiences and perceptions while working during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The nurses seemed very ready and eager to discuss their experiences and were forthcoming with personal impressions and anecdotes, which justified this data gathering method. Responses from each of the nurses varied based on their experience in different departments, and questions slightly differed for each participant depending on the protocols and procedures of their department and hospitals where they worked. The fact that their perceptions were subjective, and influenced by the intense stress of working during the COVID-19 pandemic, could have been seen as a barrier to gaining objective insights as to what actually occurred during the pandemic. However, because this inquiry is related to the stressor-caused impacts to mental well-being, burnout, and job satisfaction, the nurses' perceptions of harm is more important than an objective summation of actual harms that occurred.

Pseudonyms for each of the participants were used in order to keep all identifying information confidential. For privacy purposes, the NICU nurse will be referred to as Anne, the PACU nurse will be referred to as Melissa, the surgical ICU nurse will be referred to as John, and the ER nurse will be referred to as Mary.

Results

The data resulting from interviews provided a range of results that differed depending on the healthcare organization where each registered nurse worked and the department they worked in during the COVID-19 pandemic. Based on responses, the results were synthesized into three categories: emotional effects, nurse incivility, and job satisfaction and burnout. The general emotional effects and experiences with nurse incivility were somewhat similar among all the participants. However, there were differences in levels of job satisfaction and burnout that depended on the protocols and procedures of the hospitals where each nurse worked.

The causes of emotional effects on nurses were rooted in the significant increase in patient death they experienced, and the no-visitor policy that went into effect at all hospitals and forced nurses to witness patients dying alone with no family or friends present. All four of the registered nurses stated that the lack of visiting family members to COVID-19 patients took the highest toll on their mental health, because they had to provide all emotional support for patients, many of whom were dying, and because they had to witness the intense sadness and anguish of patients suffering and/or dying alone. Mary, the ER nurse, said that ER nurses working through the pandemic had a lot of mental and emotional damage due to the no-visitor policy, which resulted in nurses witnessing patients dying alone on a daily basis. The no-visitor policy also resulted in an exponential increase in physical and verbal violence directed at ER nurses when patients and family members learned that they could not be together in the ER unit. This further exacerbated the negative emotional effects that nurses experienced when working during the COVID-19 pandemic. All nurses interviewed asserted that their work hours increased throughout the pandemic; which they said exacerbated the amount of burnout they experienced. One nurse, Melissa, said that the longer hours also contributed to negative emotional effects because she was

forced to spend much less time at home with her husband and young children. All nurses stated that the significant increase in patient death during the COVID-19 pandemic negatively affected their mental health and wellbeing. While the emotional impact on nurses of witnessing a surge in patient deaths was expected, the severe impact of the no-visitor rules on the mental health and wellbeing of nurses was not anticipated.

Although it has been long present in the healthcare industry, nurse incivility, or bullying among nurses, significantly increased during the pandemic. All four nurses interviewed associated this increase with the rising level of stress in the workplace environment caused in part by the significant increase in patient deaths during the pandemic. Anne, a NICU nurse, stated that “after 35 years in the industry, nurse incivility [was] at an all-time high.” She attributed it to the emotional stress of the pandemic which led to increased “cattiness” among nurses. Anne also stated that “the technology used by the younger generation of nurses reduces face-to-face conflict resolution which leads to more drama online.” Melissa emphasized that politics also played a role in the increased levels of nurse incivility within her hospital. She said that nurses who believed in vaccinations and anti-vaccination nurses tended to exhibit a great deal of animosity and incivility toward each other. Mary, like the other nurses, attributed the high nurse incivility levels to the high stress work environment, but also to high-stress environments at home. For example, when schools closed and their children were at home during part of the pandemic, nurses became increasingly stressed about their home life, which would manifest itself at work in the form of incivility between coworkers. Mary also said that the high-stress environments created by patient care during the pandemic “mentally sent [younger nurses] over the edge,” which further exacerbated the problem of nurse incivility.

Besides the negative emotional effects and increase in nurse incivility, decreased levels of job satisfaction and increased levels of burnout are major problems that manifested in the healthcare industry during the pandemic. According to all nurses interviewed, these two problems have led to nurses taking jobs in lower-stress roles or leaving healthcare altogether. Mary asserted that the younger generation of ER nurses are leaving the emergency department after a few years, while the older generation of ER nurses often remained in the department for 10 to 25 years. John, a surgical ICU nurse, believes that “nursing is a high burnout job [and that] mentality plays a huge part in burnout because some people can’t compartmentalize their feelings and end up putting so much stress on themselves.” The majority of the nurses stated that they still loved the nursing profession, but their day-to-day satisfaction declined after about a year into the pandemic.

At the beginning of the pandemic, nurses and other healthcare professionals often supported each other in the workplace while they worked together against great odds to save patients’ lives. Accolades for nurses were prominent in the media and public support for nurses was at an all-time high. However, as the COVID-19 pandemic receded in the public mind and in the media, the accolades and support for nurses were forgotten, but the problems of shortages, nurse stress, incivility, dissatisfaction and burnout remain unresolved. This appears to have created a cycle of worsening workplace environments and serious nursing challenges that are not being addressed. Nurses interviewed for this research did not offer optimism that these problems would be solved any time in the near future.

Discussion & Conclusion

The overall objective of this research study is to examine the impacts of working through the COVID-19 pandemic on the mental wellbeing of registered nurses. Findings from interviews with registered nurses also help explore sustainable solutions to growing problems of burnout, job dissatisfaction, and nurse incivility.

A particularly harmful negative impact revealed in interviews with nurses is related to the no-visitor policies for patients instituted by hospitals during the pandemic to reduce the spread of disease. The unanticipated harms to nurses resulted from them becoming the sole source of emotional support for sick and dying COVID-19 patients instead of family and friends. This ultimately led to an increase in work-related stress and took the highest toll on the mental health and wellbeing of frontline registered nurses.

Although nurse incivility has always been a problem in the healthcare industry, it has been exacerbated since the start of the pandemic because of the high-stress environments brought on by the influx of COVID-19 patients. Other significant reasons for the increase in nurse incivility is the generational differences between nurses. Technology and social media are much more advanced than a few decades ago, and the younger generation of nurses uses these platforms on a more consistent basis than the older generation of nurses. This has led to a reduction in face-to-face conflict but also in face-to-face resolution of conflict. These generational differences and their impact on conflict resolution has increased nurse incivility in the healthcare industry. With all these negative emotional effects and increases in high-stress work environments, there has been a decrease in day-to-day job satisfaction and increase in levels of professional burnout. This manifests in nurses leaving stressful frontline roles, and even the healthcare industry as a whole, at a much faster rate. Younger nurses, or those with less than

five years of experience in the industry, state that they are not “emotionally healthy” and consider leaving the profession at a much higher rate than older nurses or those with more than 40 years of experience. This is due to insufficient staffing, lack of solutions and incentives, and the increase in nurse incivility (Stone, 2022). The growing shortages of nurses and other healthcare professionals will have various negative impacts on access to patient care by the public (Haddad et al., 2020).

The problems of nursing shortages and unhappy healthcare professionals are critical to solve, as they affect individuals and society as a whole. Both problems impact patient access to quality healthcare, because they are driving professionals away from direct patient care, which in turn affects the entire U.S. and global public, so this field of research is extremely important to everyone. From 2020 to 2021, over 100,000 registered nurses left the healthcare industry – most of whom were under the age of 35. This is the largest decline in healthcare professionals reported in the last 40 years (Auerbach et al., 2022). And this shortage is only expected to worsen as the Baby Boomer population ages and requires more healthcare (Rosseter, 2020). As the nursing shortage and need for healthcare in the U.S. rises, higher levels of morbidity, mortality, and errors made by healthcare professionals are expected, along with increased burnout and job dissatisfaction (Haddad et al., 2020).

Solutions to the issues of nursing shortages and negative impacts on wellbeing can be difficult to achieve but are paramount to ensuring quality patient care. Based on the findings from the interviews, solutions include giving nurses a greater say in policies and procedures put in place by hospital administration. An industry wide conversation about solutions to bullying among nurses in the workplace needs to be normalized and policies for resolutions to incivility need to be put in place with input from nurses themselves. Regarding mental health and

wellbeing, research shows that strategies related to nurse wellness should be introduced in nursing school to instill a culture of wellness and self-care for future healthcare professionals (Eckleberry-Hunt et al., 2009). Overall, a significant reason for the findings in these interviews – negative emotional effects, increased nurse incivility, job dissatisfaction, and professional burnout – is the growing shortage of healthcare professionals that predates the pandemic. Solutions to healthcare shortages are long term and require significant policy changes at the health system and national levels. Research is needed to find optimal solutions that lead to sustainable, longitudinal changes in the healthcare industry. The lack of sustainable solutions to these issues will lead to increased shortages of U.S. healthcare workers. This in turn will lead to even more adverse and harmful effects on the patient population, which is all of the U.S. public.

Continual research in this field is necessary to determine lasting effects of the pandemic on healthcare workers and to develop sustainable solutions. Future interview-based research projects should include a larger sample size and a wider range of healthcare professionals. A larger sample size of interview participants ensures higher significance of results and reduces any possible outliers that can be detrimental to accuracy. Although this specific project focuses on registered nurses, they are not the only healthcare professionals negatively affected by working through the pandemic. Further research in this area should look into other types of healthcare professionals and their experiences working through the pandemic.

Reflection

Reflecting on my time in the University Honors Program and working on my Senior Honors Project, I find myself sad to be completely finished with the program. I have been in the program for four years and it has been a constant in my life for my entire college experience. The topic I chose for my senior project is something I am passionate about, and I believe should be taken seriously by the public. We are entering an unprecedented new period of life after the pandemic, and we will be continuing to learn about and understand the long-term impacts of the pandemic on the healthcare industry. This research topic is something I think I should be built upon and investigated more thoroughly. Through this project, I learned so much about working in the healthcare industry that I did not expect when I wrote my proposal a few years ago. This newfound knowledge of the research topic significantly impacts my opinion on the importance of researching the effects of working through the pandemic on the wellbeing of healthcare professionals.

Of the multiple years spent and various tasks completed working on this project, I found that the most difficult was the writing of my proposal and final report. Making sure to include every aspect of this project and explaining the significance of it was very difficult for me. I, surprisingly, found that conducting the interviews and creating the poster for the conference were the easier tasks that I enjoyed doing the most. I will continue to challenge myself and work to improve my writing skills when it comes to research reports, as I am going into biological research for my profession.

Overall, I learned so much about myself through my time in the University Honors Program and working on the senior project. I learned to work through my imposter syndrome and believe in myself and that I am worthy and deserve to be in the program. I learned to speak

up about the things I believe are important and should be talked about, like the effects on the mental wellbeing of working through the pandemic on nurses and other healthcare professionals. I learned that, at the end of the day, I am a hard-working student that has strengths that can be different from what most of the students in the program have. And this has helped me to be more confident in myself and what I have to bring to the table.

References

- Auerbach, D. I. et al. (2022). A Worrisome Drop In The Number of Young Nurses. *Health Affairs*. Retrieved May 11, 2023, from <https://www.healthaffairs.org/doi/10.1377/forefront.20220412.311784>
- Center for Disease Control and Prevention. (2023, May 5). *End of the Federal COVID-19 Public Health Emergency (PHE) Declaration*. <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/your-health/end-of-phe.html#:~:text=The%20federal%20COVID%2D19%20PHE,to%20align%20with%20data%20changes>.
- Eckleberry-Hunt, J et al. (2009). Changing the Conversation from Burnout to Wellness: Physician Well Being In Residency Training Programs. *Journal of Graduate Medical Education*, 1(2), p. 225-230. doi: 10.4300/JGME-D-09-00026.1
- Haddad, L. M., Annamaraju, P., & Toney-Butler, T. J. (2020). Nursing Shortage. *Stat Pearls*, Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK493175/>
- Rosseter, R. (2020). Nursing Shortage Fact Sheet. *American Association of Colleges of Nursing*. Retrieved May 11, 2023, from <https://www.aacnnursing.org/news-data/fact-sheets/nursing-shortage>
- Sovold, Lene et al. (2021). Prioritizing the Mental Health and Well-Being of Healthcare Workers: An Urgent Global Public Health Priority. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 9(679397), p. 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2021.679397>
- Stone, A. (2022). Younger Nurses Are Leaving the Profession Because of Emotional Health. *Voice: Oncology Nursing Society*. Retrieved May 11, 2023, from <https://voice.ons.org/advocacy/younger-nurses-are-leaving-the-profession-because-of-emotional-health>